

PEVI: INTERFACE FOR RETRIEVING AND ANALYZING EXPRESSIVE MUSICAL PERFORMANCES WITH SCAPE PLOTS

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ABSTRACT

Although a variety of interfaces for music retrieval have been proposed so far, they are not always valid for retrieving classical music, a piece of which is recorded by many players. The lineup that current music retrieval systems suggest for a given musical piece is likely to be in order of sales. This is not always desired by classical music lovers, who are interested in various interpretations of a piece. In this paper, PEVI, a novel interface based on a scape plot for finding interpretations of classical music, is presented. The scape plot window, which visualizes the most similar performances of a specified scope (multiple layers) in a specified piece by using color tags, is used as the key to assigning a range of musical pieces to be referred to. Similar performances are displayed, on a different window, as their coordinates represent the similarity of two selected musical features in regard to tempo, dynamics, and delicate control within a beat. Users of PEVI are able to observe the transition of the indices of similar performances by changing the scope on the scape plot and each weight of the musical features. In this paper, the effectiveness of PEVI is discussed with an analysis of difference performances of “Romance de Amor.”

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, many music information retrieval systems have been proposed. We can easily find songs that are similar to a favorite piece or are cover songs. Popular music lovers enjoy the benefits of the service provided by music information retrieval systems, mainly the classifying of content on the basis of collaborative filtering approaches. By contrast, these services are not always scrupulous enough for classical music listeners. One of the big differences between classical music and popular music is that there exist plenty of performances of a particular musical piece in the genre of classical music. For classical music listeners, the differences of each performer's (conductor's) interpretations or expressions are important.

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Recommendations made by existing music information retrieval systems, such as instrumentations that are similar to query tune or a lineup of bestselling performances, are often not those desired by classical music listeners.

The goal of this paper is to provide such classical music listeners with a music retrieval interface that can also be used as a tool for active music listening [1]. For this goal, musical features such as tempo, dynamics, and delicate control within a beat should be used as the indices of similarity. One such implementation is Maezawa et al.'s “Query-by-Conducting” [2]. It makes use of global tempo transition information given by a user's conducting actions in order to search for similar performances.

It is desirable that the user can specify the scope (part) of the performance to be searched. Interpretation or expression of an expressive musical performance is essentially multi-layered, from each note-level, phrase-level, and section-level expression. A function for assigning the scope of a performance is especially required for dealing with classical music. As a tool for visualizing expressive music performances, C. Sapp proposed a visualization called the “scape plot” that shows the most similar performances of a specified scope (multiple layers) in a specified piece by using color tags [3]. The “scape plot” itself is static, and it does not show the second most similar data and below. In this paper, we propose an interface for retrieving and analyzing expressive performances of classical music called “PEVI.” The main feature of PEVI is the ability to use the scape plot as an interface to indicate the scope of a performance that is specified.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the possibility of being able to use a scape plots as an interface for music information retrieval and as an analysis system for classical music is described. In Section 3, an outline of PEVI is described. The possibilities of PEVI are discussed on the basis of an analysis of different performances of “Romance De Amor” in Section 4, and conclusions are in Section 6.

2. SCAPE PLOT AS PERFORMANCE RETRIEVAL INTERFACE

2.1 Scape Plot

In classical music, many artists perform from the same printed scores, but there are many different musical expressions produced by various interpretations. In addition,

a layered structure is also an important factor of musical expressions. There are cases when features of a microscopic structure are different from those of a macroscopic structure. In The Mazurka Project, C. Sapp proposed the scape plot as a way of visualizing the similarity between performances in multiple layers at the same time [3]. The scape plot has a triangular shape. Figure 1 is a sample of a scape plot.

Figure 1. Sample of a scape plot. The base vertical line is the time axis of a piece. The index color of the most similar performance of the span to the query is plotted at the vertex of the equilateral triangle, the base of which is the “scope.”

The base of the scape plot represents the time axis of a piece; in other words, the left vertex means the start, and the right vertex means the end of a piece. When a section of the piece or the base of a scape plot is chosen, a triangle that has a section specified as the base is decided, and the top vertex of the triangle is colored to indicate the most similar performance. Each performance is assigned a unique hue. The top vertex of the scape plot shows the most similar performance in regard to the whole piece. Thus, the scape plot shows the most similar performance in every time scale at the same time.

2.2 Using Scape Plot as Span Controller for Calculating Similarity

The scape plot is quite good for use as a visualizer of expressive musical performances. However, it can only visualize the most similar performance of each scope. The remaining performances are not visualized. We also cannot know how similar performances are. We solve these problems and propose a novel system that uses the scape plot as not only a way of visualizing but also as a user interface for giving a scope in order to calculate the similarity of performances, the results of which, including the invisible information on the scape plot, are displayed in another area. Thus, we will be able to understand the performances in detail by watching the real-time trajectories of similar performances while listening to the query performance.

Important features that identify an expression are, for example, tempo, dynamics, timbre, and expression within

a beat. Above all, tempo and dynamic features have a large effect on musical expressions and are extracted relatively easily and correctly, so they are frequently used as tools for comparing expressions, as is also adopted in the scape plot. In addition to tempo and dynamic features, the proposed system is designed to deal with features related to delicate control within a beat.

3. PEVI

3.1 Overview

PEVI is a novel interface based on the scape plot for finding interpretations of classical music. An overview of PEVI is shown in Figure 2. The first thing that users of PEVI do is to give the query performance of a music piece. Then, the user can limit the number of performance examples retrieved, which contributes to improve time resolution of visualization. Users are allowed to give weight to each feature considered for similarity calculation.

Figure 2. Overview of PEVI

The functions of visualization that PEVI offers are the scape plot, which is also used as a scope controller, the piano roll of the query and the selected performances which are retrieved, line graphs of the selected features, and real-time trajectories of the performances in a selected two-feature plane (so called the “performance worm” [4]) and in polar coordinates.

An example of the GUI of PEVI (top page) is shown in Figure 3. This figure is a snapshot of the visualizing of performances of Prelude Op. 28 No. 7 in A major by F. Chopin in the tempo-dynamics plane. The half-tone dot meshing area in the left figure is the span used for calculating similarity. When users push the play button, they can listen to the span of the query performance while watching animated visualizations of the trajectories of the performances that are retrieved.

Figure 3. Main GUI of PEVI. Half-tone dot meshing area in the left figure is the span used for calculating similarity. Color index represents name of performer.

Figure 4. Sample of visualizations with PEVI

Figure 4 shows samples of visualization of the performances retrieved. The left shows the visualization in a polar coordinate, and the right shows the performance worm. Users of PEVI are able to change the query by selecting a colored index in these visualizations just like web-surfing.

3.2 Calculating Similarity

We use Pearson product-moment correlation as the similarity between each feature of performances. The sequence x means the data of a query, and the sequence y means the data of one of the target performances. \bar{x} and \bar{y} mean arithmetic averages of sequence $x = \{x_i\}$ and sequence $y = \{y_i\}$. Then, Pearson coefficient, often called an “r-value” in statistics, is defined as:

$$\text{Peason}(x, y) = \frac{\sum_n(x_n - \bar{x})(y_n - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_n(x_n - \bar{x})^2 \sum_n(y_n - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

The value range of Pearson correlation is -1.0 to $+1.0$. The 1.0 indicates an identical match between two performances.

Figure 5 shows an example of the Pearson correlation of tempo between two performances. It shows there is a strong correlation in the scope from beat 1 to 3, almost no correlation in the scope from beat 3 to 10, and a negative correlation in the scope from beat 7 to 10.

Figure 5. Sample of Pearson product-moment

3.3 Data Format of the Performances

PEVI accepts performance data that are written in compliance with the CrestMuseXML and DeviationInstanceXML formats, which are compatible with CrestMusePEDB¹, a database for expressive performances [5].

The objects of the collection stored in CrestMusePEDB are pieces of classical music up until the early twentieth century whose copyrights are expired, mainly piano pieces composed by J. S. Bach, W. A. Mozart, L. V. Beethoven, and F. Chopin, and pieces that are often covered by earlier studies or are interesting as research objects are chosen. Performance expressions are labeled by hand from recordings of excellent performances. Transitions of tempo and dynamics are extracted at the beat level, and timings and the shifts of the dynamics of each tone are extracted at the MIDI level. Deviations of each tone from a printed score are detected as a musical expression. The data are written in compliance with MusicXML. We obtain tempo and dynamics transitions in increments of a quarter note.

4. USER EVALUATION

In this section, a preliminary user evaluation of PEVI is described. The goal of implementing PEVI is to expand the possibility of using the scape plot to retrieve and analyze classical music, where expressing the notes of a score makes much sense. The effectiveness of the visualization, usability, possibilities, and problems were collected by using a questionnaire.

Seven university students (from 20 to 24 years of age), whose musical experience ranged from the novice level to more than 10 years of piano playing, participated in the evaluation. After an explanation of how to use PEVI, the participants were made to use it freely to access performances until they judged that they had fully used the functions of PEVI. The experimenters explained the meaning of some of the musical terms in the GUI to the novice participants during the procedure on demand. The average operation time was around one hour.

The participants were asked to score the following items on a scale of 1 to 6 (1: lowest, 6: highest): a) intuitiveness of visualizing two styles (polar coordinate and

¹ <http://www.crestmuse.jp/pedb/>

performance worm), b) effectiveness of visualizing delicate control within a beat to listen to the differences between performances, c) effectiveness of using the scape plot to assign a “scope” to calculate similarity, d) effectiveness of giving weight to each feature, and some items regarding the total usability of PEVI. In addition, participants were asked to write their opinions freely regarding the total usability.

As for the visualization, the participants preferred the performance worm style to the polar coordinate style.

The effectiveness of visualizing delicate control within a beat was given significantly high scores ($P < 0.05$) by the participants who had some musical experience.

In comparison, participants with little musical experience answered “I can hear the differences between performances, but I’m not sure what makes the differences. From the start, I have never listened to music knowing there exists differences among the performances.” These results illustrate that PEVI is an effective tool for enhancing the pleasantness of listening to music for listeners with some musical experience rather than for novice listeners.

As for the total usability, the intuitiveness of the GUI and pleasantness were given high scores, 5.8 and 5.0 respectively. We may conclude that PEVI is a novel tool for active music listening, especially for classical music.

5. ANALYZING “ROMANCE DE AMOR”

PEVI is expected to be used to analyze how each of the performers (performances) affects each other, which is regarded as a typical theme of musicology. This usage was originally pointed out by C. Sapp as an application of the scape plot in [6]. However, PEVI, which is implemented as an interactive application that enables users to change weights for the features and the span, provides users with smoother operation in order to achieve this goal. In this section, the potential of PEVI is discussed by introducing examples of performances of “Romance de Amor” for guitar.

“Romance de Amor” is a Spanish folksong. The first eight bars at the beginning are shown in Figure 6. After being used as the theme of the French film “Jeux interdits,” it has been one of the most famous pieces of music for guitar and has been performed by many guitar players, including professionals and amateurs. It is not so strange to frame the hypothesis that the relationship between master and disciple, nationalities, and age may cause there to be similarities in performances. This hypothesis is examined by retrieving performances of “Romance de Amor” by using PEVI.

Figure 6. Beginning part of “Romance de Amor”

The retrieved guitarists were Narciso Yepes, Kiyoshi Shomura, Kazuhito Yamashita, Shin-ichi Fukuda, Daisuke Suzuki, Yasuji Ohagi, and Kaori Muraji. First, “Romance de Amor” was made known to the world by the virtuoso performance of Yepes. Shomura is one of a few Japanese guitarists who studied under Yepes. Suzuki, Ohagi, and Muraji studied under Fukuda, who is a friend of Shomura. Both Yamashita and Fukuda and both Ohagi and Muraji are guitarists of the same generation, respectively. Suzuki is a Jazz guitar player as well as a classic guitar player. Ohagi and Muraji are the youngest among the seven guitarists and regarded to play the latest interpretation of the song. Muraji is the only female guitarist of the seven. Yamashita is known for his transcendent technique and is regarded as a unique guitarist by the others.

The performance data for this analysis were obtained with experienced guitar players’ iterated listening and revision, using a tool² for creating a performance data

Figure 7. Analyzing guitar performances of “Romance de Amor”

² <http://en.sourceforge.jp/projects/cmxf/>

provided by the CrestMusePEDB committee.

The result of the analysis is shown in Figure 7. The right side of Figure 7 shows the analysis when Shomura's performance was set as the query performance. There was no distinctive similarity between Yepes' and Shomura's performances when the weights for the tempo, dynamics, and delicate control within a beat were equally given. In accordance with a gain in the weight for dynamics, the area that shows Yepes' performance (magenta) in the scape plot expanded at the first half. We could find similarity in the expression of dynamics between Shomura and Suzuki's performances. When the weights for tempo, dynamics, and expression in a beat were set to 1:2:0, we could see similarity between Shomura's and Muraji's performances.

The left side of Figure 7 shows the results when queries were set to Suzuki, Ohagi, Muraji, and their teacher, Fukuda, respectively. Each weight for tempo, dynamics, and expression within a beat were set to 1:1:1. In the plot for Fukuda (around the center area), we could see a big yellow area that represented Ohagi and a big purple one that represented Muraji. We could see that red represented Suzuki, the area of which was small compared with those for yellow and purple, at the base of the triangle. This shows that Suzuki inherited local features of expression from his teacher Fukuda the most. The second and third performances most similar to Fukuda's were also those of his pupils. These observations suggest that Fukuda's pupils inherited features of expression from their teacher, Fukuda, the most. The next performance similar to Fukuda's was that of Yamashita, who is of the same generation as Fukuda.

The three scape plots at the most left side are those of Fukuda's three pupil guitarists. Some similarities were observed between Suzuki's and Muraji's performances. They were especially similar at the latter half, where expression in regard to dynamics was similar to that of their teacher, Fukuda. Compared with Suzuki's and Muraji's scape plot, Ohagi's one looked different. It seems that performers of the same generation may play in a different style, even when their teacher is the same.

Figure 8 shows snapshots of the transition of the performances, where Ohagi's performance was set as the query. This shows that Muraji's performance (in pink) got closer to Ohagi's, replacing Fukuda's (in blue) between bars 5 and 8.

Figure 8. Transition of the performances, where Ohagi's performance was given as the query. Left and right figures are snapshots at bars 5 and 8, respectively.

6. DISCUSSION

PEVI enables interpretations to be retrieved and analyzed by focusing on factors of musical features. We expect that the main users of PEVI will be classical music enthusiasts and scholars. For example, PEVI could be used for an analysis of student/teacher similarities or genealogical studies of musical performers. PEVI will be useful for not only comparing the degree of similarity but also for knowing which factors of musical expressions or which part of a performance are affected by a teacher. For the player, the findings obtained by using our system can be used as a reference. The features in the macroscopic layers are especially difficult to understand only by ear.

Of course, PEVI will also be useful for those beginning to listen to classical music. Comparing expressions is one way to enjoy classical music, but it is difficult to find differences of expressions by using only one's own ear. PEVI enables these differences to be understood by listening to and "touching" the performances and by investigating specific factors. If our system can work on mobile devices, it will be of great use to many classical music listeners.

The database of musical expressions enabled us to make our system. Separating each tone from recordings is helpful for manipulating or understanding expressions. Recently, audio source separation techniques have been rapidly developing [7,8,9]. We can easily separate one note from recordings. This will encourage construction of separated music databases and advance automatic music-understanding technologies. If a bigger musical expression database were constructed, our system would be able to deal with many more performances in the future. Furthermore, if musical features can be detected perfectly and automatically from live performances, we can compare our own performances to those of virtuoso performances. PEVI will be able to help every performer who learns how to express themselves by listening to professional players and both music school students and amateur players.

If we use expression within a beat, we can compare the musical features of performances in detail. Pianists do not always play left- and right-hand notes together, according to aural traditions, although they are written as simultaneities in a printed score. Deviations of the left and right hand produce various expressions and characterize the performance. In addition, articulations such as legato and staccato are also important musical features for identifying interpretations. Individual performers will be characterized more minutely.

As future work to further develop our system, we would like to reflect on other important musical features when retrieving interpretations, for example, the timbre and expression within a beat. Currently, PEVI deals with only two musical features: tempo and dynamics transition. If we use timbre, PEVI is useful for investigating interpretations of performances played as instrumentals with instruments that have much more ability to change timbre than does the piano, for example, the guitar and other strings.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, PEVI, a novel interface based on the scape plot for finding interpretations of a specified piece, was presented. The scape plot has two problems: it is not able to visualize performances that are not the most similar and it cannot control the weights of musical features. The interface solves these problems by displaying the invisible information on another area and adding a function to change the weights of tempo and dynamics transition and to redraw the scape plot. As a result, we can easily find objective performances for any musical feature of a specified performer in a pool. As future work, we would like to add functions for selecting target performances, mixing expressions of multiple performances, playing new expressions, and reflecting other musical features, for example, timbre, expression within a beat, and articulations in interpretation retrieval.

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